

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF PSYCHOLOGICAL SUPPORT IN CRISIS SITUATIONS USING AN INFORMATION SYSTEM BASED ON GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract

One of the pressing problems under conditions of prolonged exposure to stress factors is the implementation of effective online psychological support services. This article investigates the use of generative artificial intelligence (GAI) for creating an information system designed to support individuals in difficult life situations (providing self-help and self-reflection recommendations) as well as to assist the professional activities of psychologists. The proposed system generates knowledge-based recommendations using semantic content retrieval implemented with a domain-adapted LLaMA-based LLM with Retrieval-Augmented Generation architecture and context-aware personalization (users' emotional state, interactions history, and situational factors). The implemented approach combines semantic text generalization, empathetic formulation of recommendations, and access to a psychological knowledge base online. This significantly increases the accessibility and speed of psychological assistance. Experimental testing of the prototype, evaluated using Precision@k, Recall@k, and MRR metrics, demonstrated high relevance, completeness, and quality of recommendation ranking. A sociological survey of potential users and professionals confirmed the relevance and feasibility of employing the developed online service in crisis situations.

Keywords: psychological support, generative artificial intelligence, large language model, retrieval-augmented generation, knowledge-based filtering, semantic embedding, natural language processing.

1. Introduction and Related Work

Modern social and security challenges associated with martial law, mass traumatic events, and increased psychological stress on the population lead to a growing need for accessible and scalable means of psychological support. The prolonged impact of stress factors caused by hostilities is accompanied by large-scale human losses, the death of loved ones, the destruction of housing infrastructure, forced displacement, regular air-raid alerts, shelling, and other dangerous factors. This leads to persistent psychoemotional stress and depletion of individuals' adaptive potential.

Traditional forms of psychological assistance are not always able to respond promptly to increasing demand, especially under crisis conditions, which necessitates expanding the use of online services [1]. Existing research in the field of psychological care demonstrates the effective use of online platforms and chatbots for diagnosis, consultations with specialists, social support, and enhancing patients' mental resilience [2, 3]. New opportunities for their development are provided by rapid advances in artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, particularly natural language processing (NLP) methods and large language models (LLMs) as representatives of generative artificial intelligence (GAI) [2]. Current research shows that use of LLMs enables the analysis of a person's mental state through semantic interpretation of natural language, identification of intentions, mood, emotional markers, and cognitive patterns, as well as the generation of personalized dialog recommendations that take into the context of interactions and individual characteristics of the user [3-7].

However, despite the significant potential of LLMs, they have several limitations, in particular their knowledge is constrained by pre-training data and their

tendency to hallucinate, which requires additional mechanisms for result validation and knowledge control. Their unpredictable nature can lead to erroneous, potentially harmful recommendations and unexpected negative consequences [8]. There are also risks such as privacy breaches, biases, and security issues [9]. Unlike general-purpose dialog agents, virtual psychologists require specialized training or fine-tuning of LLMs and multi-level filtering of responses that takes into account evidence-based psychological support protocols and the need to refer users to a specialist in critical cases. Addressing these challenges requires the development of information systems that implement ethical, transparent, and controlled approaches aimed at reducing the risks of incorrect or unsupported advice and combining AI with professional psychological support. A survey conducted among potential users and professional psychologists confirmed the demand for such intelligent psychological support services (fig. 1).

An effective approach to improving the reliability of generative models is their integration with the Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) architecture. Integrating LLMs with RAG provides access to a domain-specific knowledge base with semantic search prior to response generation, increasing the relevance, validity, and explainability of recommendations, reducing the risk of hallucinations, and enabling knowledge updates without retraining the model [10, 11]. However, the practical implementation of such an approach in the domain of psychological care remains insufficiently studied and requires further development.

The purpose of this article is to develop and research an information system for psychological support based on generative artificial intelligence models with integrated RAG architecture, designed to provide prompt, accessible, and evidence-based

recommendations for individuals in difficult life situations and for professional psychologists.

Figure 1. Assessment of User Needs for Online Psychological Support Systems

2. Information system architecture

The developed psychological support information system implements a multi-level modular architecture that provides a coordinated integration of generative language models, natural language processing methods, and infrastructure for data storage and synchronization. This approach allows for a clear delineation of the functional roles of system components, ensures scalability and controllability of recommendation generation, and supports the personalized nature of the recommendations.

1. *Client Level*. The client level is represented by a web interface designed for two user roles: individuals seeking psychological support and psychological specialists. The interface provides authentication, interaction session management, access to dialogue history, and role-based access to system functionality.

2. *Generative Level (LLM Level)*. The generative level of the system is implemented using the large language models LLaMA and ChatGPT, which serve as tools for generating dialog responses and textual recommendations. Access to the generative services is provided through application programming interfaces (APIs), enabling interaction with the client application without requiring client-side computation.

The LLaMA model serves as the primary generative component for the semantic interpretation of user queries, conducting dialogue, and the generation of personalized recommendations. It is used without parameter modification (i.e., without fine-tuning), and its domain adaptation is achieved through integration with the Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) architecture. The model operates as a private cloud service de-

ployed within an on-premise infrastructure. Additionally, the system supports integration with ChatGPT via API as an alternative generative component for producing explanations or enriching response content. This ensures architectural flexibility and enables the use of models hosted in the public cloud.

3. *Domain-Specific Knowledge Access Level (Retrieval Level)*. The knowledge access level implements a knowledge-based approach to recommendation generation and is responsible for the intelligent filtering of information. It is built using the LlamaIndex framework, which enables the indexing of professional textual sources (psychological literature, counseling techniques, support scenarios, and recommendation protocols), semantic retrieval of relevant fragments, and their integration into the response generation context within the RAG architecture. In the proposed implementation, RAG expands the model context by incorporating relevant fragments from the domain-specific knowledge repository prior to answer generation. This increases the relevance, validity, and controllability of recommendations and reduces the risk of unsupported or irrelevant advice in the provision of psychological support.

Contextual personalization of recommendations is achieved by taking into account the results of semantic retrieval, the history of previous interaction sessions, and the situational context of the user's request. This approach enables intelligent information filtering within the system's recommendation logic.

A cloud-based NoSQL database built on the Firebase platform is used for real-time data storage, synchronization, and exchange. This component provides storage of dialogue history, access to a repository of

professional information sources in JSON format, and support for complex queries and asynchronous interaction between users and psychologists. This contributes to the consistency of recommendations and the continuity of the psychological support process.

4. *Natural Language Processing Level (NLP Level)*. The NLP level is implemented using the TextBlob library, which is based on NLTK and Pattern. The components of this level provide: preliminary analysis of user queries, text tokenization and linguistic normalization, extraction of linguistic and emotional features, sentiment analysis and emotion detection, post-processing of generated responses. The extracted features are used to assess the user's psycho-emotional state and serve as parameters for intelligent filtering in the formation of personalized recommendations.

Figure 2. The generalized logic of component interaction

The proposed architecture integrates generative artificial intelligence with knowledge-based mechanisms for intelligent information filtering and provides a technological foundation for the experimental evaluation of the system in the field of psychological support.

3. Knowledge-Based Filtering with Semantic and Contextual Adaptation for Recommendation Generation

Information filtering in the system is implemented using a knowledge-based approach based on vector semantic representations of text, supplemented with contextual adaptation of the results. Personalized recommendations are generated by approximating a utility function:

$$f(u, i, c): U \times I \times C \rightarrow \mathcal{R}, \quad (1)$$

where $U = \{u_j \mid j = 1, \dots, m\}$ is the set of users, including the roles of patient and psychologist;

$I = \{i_l \mid l = 1, \dots, n\}$ is the set of information objects in the professional knowledge repository (therapeutic techniques, counseling scenarios, diagnostic approaches, psychoeducational materials, and self-help recommendations);

C is the set of contexts that includes, for each user $u \in U$, the user's role, the history of current and previous dialogues, and situational and emotional factors;

\mathcal{R} is an ordered numerical space of utility values defined over the set of real numbers ($\mathcal{R} \subseteq \mathbb{R}$), whose ordering is used to rank information objects.

The value of the function $f(u_j, i_l, c_j)$ is interpreted as the predicted relevance of the information object i_l for the user u_j , given the user's context c_j .

Information objects $i \in I$, represented by a single semantic embedding in the knowledge base, are used to generate recommendations at different levels of ab-

After response generation, the post-processing and filtering stage performs semantic validation of the generated response with respect to the user's context-enriched query, safety and ethical filtering, role-based adaptation of the generated content, removal of redundant or potentially unsafe fragments, and formatting of the final response before it is delivered to the user.

The system architecture combines a private cloud generative service based on the LLaMA model (on-premise private cloud AI service) with a public cloud infrastructure for data storage and synchronization. This approach ensures a balance between confidentiality, control over data processing, and scalability. The overall interaction logic of the system components is presented in figure 2.

straction. For psychologists, the system produces recommendations in the form of professional methods and counseling scenarios. For individuals seeking psychological support, the same knowledge is delivered as generalized guidance and self-help instructions that comply with ethical and informational constraints. This approach ensures the unity knowledge-based filtering regardless of the user's role.

In the proposed architecture, the user's context is directly incorporated into the process of generating the semantic representation of the query. The text query q of user u_j , interacting with the system, is concatenated with their context c_j :

$$q' = c_j \oplus q, \quad (2)$$

where \oplus denotes the ordered concatenation of text sequences.

The context-enriched query q' and the information objects i from the knowledge base repository undergo preprocessing at the NLP level of the system (tokenization, lexical normalization of the text, and extraction of linguistic features), after which they are mapped into a shared high-dimensional semantic space of embeddings generated by the encoder of the LLaMA model:

$$e(q', c_j) \in \mathbb{R}^k, e(i_l) \in \mathbb{R}^k. \quad (3)$$

where $e(q', c_j)$ is the embedding vector of the context-enriched query q' ;

$e(i_l)$ is the embedding vector of the information object i_l , $l = 1, \dots, n$;

\mathbb{R}^k is the k -dimensional real vector space, in which are presented semantic representations of text data.

The relevance of each information object $i_l \in I$ to the user u_j 's query q' is defined as the proximity measure between the embedding vectors of the context-enriched query and the information object:

$$f(u_j, i_l, c_j) = \text{sim}(e(q', c_j), e(i_l)). \quad (4)$$

Before computing the proximity measures, the embedding vectors are normalized using L2 normalization:

$$\hat{e} = \frac{e}{\|e\|_2}, \quad (5)$$

where $\|e\|_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^k e_t^2}$ is the euclidean norm of a vector.

This enables the computation of the cosine similarity measure as the scalar product of the embedding vectors:

$$\text{sim}(e(q', c_j), e(i_l)) = e(q', c_j) \cdot e(i_l). \quad (6)$$

After computing the utility function $f(u_j, i_l, c_{u_j})$ for all objects $i_l \in I$ the objects are ranked in descending order of relevance, and those with the highest utility function values are selected. The resulting set of relevant information objects is used as the knowledge context in the retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) mechanism. The ChatGPT API is employed to generate textual responses based on the selected knowledge context.

Thus, the information system implements knowledge-based filtering with semantic and contextual adaptation for generating personalized recommendations. The context is modeled through an extended embedding-based query in a shared latent semantic space, consistent with the principles of modern RAG architectures. LLaMA provides the core functionality for semantic search and generation within a private cloud environment, while ChatGPT is used as an optional external generative component without interfering with the retrieval mechanism. The proposed approach enables semantically grounded, context-adaptive, and role-sensitive recommendation generation

while minimizing lexical mismatch and excessive generalization.

4. Results and Discussion

The developed system is available online at any time, enabling the provision of initial psychological support outside face-to-face consultations and promoting continuity of interaction between the client and the psychologist. The software prototype of the system was developed as part of a master's thesis conducted under the supervision of the author. To begin working with the system web application, the user performs authentication, after which the main page is displayed (fig. 3).

After authentication, the user can submit queries and receive responses from the system in a dialogue format. The history of previous dialogues is stored and used as context for generating responses to subsequent user queries, which enables context-dependent personalization of recommendations.

At the stage of preliminary query processing, implemented at the Natural Language Processing level of the system architecture, text analysis is performed using polarity and subjectivity metrics. Polarity reflects the emotional tone of a message, whereas subjectivity characterizes the degree of personal or emotional evaluation expressed in the statement. The polarity value ranges from -1 to 1, where negative values correspond to negative emotional tone (-1 representing the most negative value), while positive values correspond to positive tone (1 representing the most positive value). The subjectivity score ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 corresponds to a completely objective statement and 1 indicates a fully subjective expression.

Figure 3. Main page of the psychological support system web application

Table 1 presents examples of the interpretation of several user queries during the preliminary analysis stage. As shown in the examples, the message "I have trouble sleeping at night. What can I do?" demonstrates slightly positive polarity and moderate subjectivity. The message "What if without it I can do something bad to myself?" exhibits strongly negative polarity and a high degree of subjectivity, whereas the short message

"Are you sure?" shows relatively positive polarity combined with a high level of subjectivity. The obtained polarity and subjectivity values are further used by the system as additional features for assessing the user's psycho-emotional state and are incorporated into the query context during the recommendation generation process.

Figures 4 and 5 present examples of viewing dialogues stored in the cloud database of the Firebase platform. Figure 4 shows a fragment of a dialogue with an example of recommendations generated by the system for a user who requested support for anger management. Figure 5 presents an example of recommendations generated in response to a query related to coping

with a depressed emotional state. These dialogues can be directly reviewed and analyzed by a professional psychologist in order to provide additional professional support to the client. In addition, the dialogue history is used by the system as context when generating responses to the current and subsequent user queries, taking into account the user's role in the system.

Table 1.

Examples of interpretation of user queries at the preprocessing and analysis stage

No.	User query	Polarity	Subjectivity
1	I have trouble sleeping at night. What can I do?	0.15	0.35
2	What if without it I can do something bad to myself?	-0.7	0.67
3	Are you sure?	0.5	0.89

Figure 4. Example of generated recommendations for anger management

In cases where the analysis of the user's message indicates a potentially critical or unsafe psycho-emotional state, the system generates recommendations aimed at initial self-help and emotional stabilization,

while strongly advising the user to seek assistance from a qualified specialist. An example of such a response is shown in figure 6.

Figure 5. Example of generated recommendations for coping with a depressed emotional state

Figure 6. Example of a response with self-help recommendations in a critical condition and a recommendation to contact a specialist

In the presented example, the system responds to the user query *"I want to hurt myself"* by generating a message expressing empathy and support. The system emphasizes that the person is not alone and that help is available. At the same time, it recommends contacting a professional psychologist or psychotherapist and, in situations where there is a risk to life, immediately reaching out to emergency services or crisis hotlines. The user is also advised to remain in a safe place and, if possible, avoid being alone.

The presented examples demonstrate that the system is capable of maintaining a dialogue with the user

while generating responses based on the principles of empathetic communication, providing psychological support and offering recommendations aimed at stabilizing the user's emotional state.

Thus, the results of the prototype system implementation demonstrate its potential for use by individuals facing difficult life situations in the form of a virtual assistant for obtaining personalized self-help recommendations. For professional psychologists, the system can serve as a decision-support tool by automating the selection of relevant psychological techniques,

counseling scenarios, and support plans according to the specific situation of the client.

5. Experimental Studies and System Quality Evaluation

The prototype of the psychological support information system was validated through an experimental evaluation of information filtering quality using classical information retrieval metrics.

For the experimental evaluation, a set of test queries was formed to simulate typical scenarios of user requests in difficult life situations as well as professional queries from psychologists:

$$Q = \{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_N\}, \quad (7)$$

where Q denotes the set of test queries.

To construct the test queries and the corresponding reference relevant answers, expert psychologists were involved. In total $N = 75$ queries were generated and classified into thematic categories for patients and professional psychologists (tables 2 and 3). Such classification ensures a representative and balanced set of scenarios, enabling the evaluation of system performance in different contexts of psychological support.

For each query q_i , a set of relevant information objects from the professional knowledge repository was defined:

$$R(q_i) = \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_m\}, \quad (8)$$

where $R(q_i)$ denotes the set of information objects $i \in I$ that are relevant for generating an appropriate psychological recommendation.

Table 2.

Categories of user queries		
Category	Description	Number of queries
Stress and anxiety	Symptoms of stress, anxiety, and emotional exhaustion	10
Loss and life crises	Loss of loved ones, divorce, major life changes	8
Crisis psycho-emotional states	Suicidal thoughts, severe emotional destabilization	5
Interpersonal conflicts	Problems in family, workplace, friendships, bullying	8
Self-help and self-regulation	Requests for self-help and personal development recommendations	6
Psychological support in crisis situations related to war events	Psychological support for military personnel and civilians during shelling, air-raid alerts, loss of housing, property or relatives, after injury or captivity	8

Table 3.

Categories of professional psychologist queries		
Category	Description	Number of queries
Selection of psychological methods	Choosing optimal psychological techniques for a specific client	8
Support planning	Development of psychological support plans	6
Structured counseling scenarios	Examples of structured counseling scenarios for working with a patient	5
Diagnostic approaches	Methods for diagnosing psycho-emotional states	5
Psychological support in crisis situations related to war events	Selection of methods and support plans for military personnel and civilians affected by combat, trauma, shelling, or losses	6

For each query q_i , the developed information system generated a list of information objects recommended for response generation:

$$S(q_i) = \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_k\}, \quad (9)$$

where $S(q_i)$ represents a list of knowledge-base information objects ranked in descending order of relevance, and k is the fixed number of recommended objects used to ensure comparability of results.

To evaluate the quality of the developed prototype information system, classical metrics from information retrieval and recommender systems were used: Precision@k, Recall@k, and Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR). These metrics allow a quantitative assessment of relevance, completeness, and ranking quality of the retrieved information objects. The metrics were calculated using the following formulas.

1. Precision@k evaluates filtering accuracy, i.e., the proportion of relevant results among the top k recommended objects:

$$Precision@k(q_i) = \frac{|S(q_i) \cap R(q_i)|}{k}. \quad (10)$$

This metric indicates how effectively the system avoids informational noise and prevents irrelevant recommendations, which is critically important in the psychological domain.

2. Recall@k measures the completeness of access to relevant knowledge (the proportion of relevant information objects retrieved):

$$Recall@k(q_i) = \frac{|S(q_i) \cap R(q_i)|}{|R(q_i)|}. \quad (11)$$

This metric characterizes the system's ability to identify relevant information objects without losing important knowledge, which is particularly important in decision-support systems for professional psychologists.

3. MRR evaluates the ranking quality of recommendations, defined as the average reciprocal rank of the first relevant result:

$$RR(q_i) = \frac{1}{rank_i}, \quad (12)$$

where $rank_i$ is the position of the first relevant information object in the list $S(q_i)$.

The average value of this metric is calculated as:

$$MRR = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N RR(q_i). \quad (13)$$

This metric is particularly important for dialog systems, as it reflects how quickly a user or a specialist receives a relevant recommendation.

Metric values were calculated for each query $q \in Q$ and averaged across the entire set of test queries:

$$Precision@k = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N Precision@k(q_i), \quad (14)$$

$$Recall@k = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N Recall@k(q_i). \quad (15)$$

In the experiments, $k = 5$ was used, which corresponds to a typical number of recommendations in decision-support systems.

To analyze the impact of the implemented recommendation generation approach, the metrics **Precision@k**, **Recall@k**, and **MRR** were calculated for three system configurations: without RAG (LLM without retrieval); RAG without contextual information; with contextual personalization. Table 4 presents the results obtained.

Table 4.

Quality evaluation of the psychological support information system

System configuration	Precision@5	Recall@5	MRR
Without RAG	0.65	0.52	0.68
RAG without contextual information	0.80	0.74	0.83
RAG with contextual personalization	0.88	0.83	0.91

The obtained results demonstrate a gradual improvement in recommendation quality with the introduction of the retrieval component and contextual adaptation. The metrics calculated without using RAG represent the baseline level of response generation based solely on the language models LLaMA/ChatGPT without access to the domain knowledge base. In this case, the relevance of recommendations is lower ($Precision@5 \approx 0.65$).

In the second experiment, a significant improvement in recommendation quality was observed due to the use of the Retrieval Augmented Generation architecture ($Precision@5 \approx 0.80$, $Recall@5 \approx 0.74$). The third experiment, which incorporated contextual personalization, demonstrated the highest values of relevance, completeness, and ranking quality ($Precision@5 \approx 0.88$, $Recall@5 \approx 0.83$).

The experiments also revealed an improvement in the speed of obtaining relevant recommendations: the MRR value increased from approximately 0.68 to 0.91, indicating better ranking quality of the retrieved results. These findings confirm the effectiveness of the knowledge-based approach using semantic search, the Retrieval Augmented Generation architecture, and contextual personalization.

Thus, the results of the experimental studies confirmed the effectiveness of the proposed approach based on the use of generative artificial intelligence. Knowledge-based filtering with semantic and contextual adaptation within the Retrieval Augmented Generation architecture enables the generation of personalized, relevant, and timely recommendations tailored to the needs of different user categories, including psychological support scenarios in crisis situations related to war events. The system demonstrates the ability to adapt recommendations to the user's emotional state without relying on rigid rule-based mechanisms, which constitutes an important advantage for applications in the field of psychological support.

6. Conclusions

This paper proposes an approach to the development of an information system for psychological support that integrates the capabilities of generative artificial intelligence, semantic search, and knowledge-based information filtering. The system architecture implements the Retrieval Augmented Generation principle, enabling the combination of generative capabilities of large language models with semantic retrieval of relevant knowledge-base objects. Additionally, a mechanism for contextual adaptation has been implemented to generate personalized recommendations considering the user's role within the system (either a patient or a psychologist).

Experimental evaluation of the proposed approach using $Precision@k$, $Recall@k$, and Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) metrics demonstrated that the application of RAG architecture in combination with contextual personalization significantly improves the relevance of recommendations, coverage of knowledge, and ranking quality compared to an approach based solely on generative language models. The prototypical system was validated, confirming its potential use as an effective online psychological support service both for users experiencing challenging life situations and for psychologists in analyzing client inquiries and preparing recommendations.

Future research directions include expanding the system's domain-specific knowledge base, enhancing methods for contextual personalization of recommendations, and conducting larger-scale experimental studies involving a broader cohort of users and psychologists to comprehensively evaluate the practical effectiveness of the proposed system.

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